

Impact of industrial logging on specific diversity and floristic composition of a tropical rainforest, case of Cotrefor-Alibuku concession forest in DRC

Kafuti C.¹, Bolaluembe P.¹, Belesi H.², Ifuta S.², Bangelesa F.¹

(1) Faculty of agronomic sciences, Department of Natural Resources Management, University of Kinshasa. PO Box 117 Kinshasa XI (DRC) / e-mail : kafuti3@gmail.com

(2) Faculty of sciences, Department of Environmental Sciences, Laboratory of Systemic, Biodiversity and Conservation, University of Kinshasa. (DRC)

doi :

Abstract

The industrial logging has in most of cases a huge impact on specific diversity and floristic composition of tropical rainforests, compromising their ability to play correctly their role. But it is alarming to note that studies related to the assessment of the industrial logging impacts on specific diversity and floristic composition have not yet been carried out in DRC, despite the intensity and the spread of logging in the country. The aim of this article is to analyze the specific diversity and floristic composition surveyed in different impact points of logging in Cotrefor-Alibuku concession forest, one year after the operation. Surfaces plots and itinerant method were used to collect floristic data. In total, 20 plots of size 30 m² have been surveyed in different impact points : the logging roads, the skid trails, the logging gaps and the log landings. An area not disturbed by logging was also sampled as a control point. The diversity and the wealth of flora, as well as the altitude and the intensity of logging operation of the impacts point have been analyzed. All the points of impact showed a specific richness from 1.3

to 2.4 times higher than that of the not disturbed site which shows a weak floristic similarity (less than 25%) with all points of impact. In terms of diversity, the Shannon index reveals that only the logging gaps ($H' = 3.04$) and the skid trails ($H' = 2.95$) are more diversified than the undisturbed site ($H' = 2.87$). On this last site, non commercial species and commercial species of Class 1 reveal the greatest proportions (22 % each one), whereas the species of the other commercial classes present significant proportions in the points of impact. Except from the logging roads, the diversity of the points of impact is inversely proportional to the intensity of logging operations. Forestry monitoring after logging seemed to be necessary in order to make profitable the positive effects and to minimize the negative effects of logging. Initially, the results found in this study can serve as a guide track for logging operations and allow forest managers and other actors to run a successful program of natural regeneration aid and to properly ensure sustainability in the management of their forests.

Keywords: Logging, specific diversity, floristic composition.

Résumé

L'exploitation industrielle du bois induit dans la plupart des cas un impact non négligeable sur la diversité spécifique et la composition floristique des forêts tropicales denses et humides compromettant leur capacité à jouer correctement leurs rôles. Cependant, il est alarmant de constater que les études dédiées à cette question sont quasiment absentes en RDC en dépit de l'ampleur de cette opération. Cet article analyse ainsi la diversité spécifique et la composition floristique relevées au niveau de différents points d'impact de l'exploitation forestière dans la concession forestière de Cotrefor-Alibuku, une année après l'opération. La collecte des données sur la flore a combiné la méthode de relevé de surface et celle dite itinérante. Les relevés de surface ont consisté à conduire des inventaires dans 20 placettes de 30 m² dans différents points d'impact de l'exploitation

: les parcs à bois, les routes d'exploitation, les pistes de débardage et les trouées d'abattage. Un site témoin au sein d'une zone forestière non encore exploitée a également été pris en considération. Une analyse des données collectées sur le terrain a été effectuée autour de la diversité et richesse de la flore mais également de l'altitude et de l'intensité de l'exploitation sur les différents points d'impact. Tous les points d'impact ont affiché une richesse spécifique de 1,3 à 2,4 fois supérieure à celle du site témoin. La flore du site témoin ne présente qu'une faible similarité (moins de 25%) avec celle de tous les sites exploités. En termes de diversité, l'indice de Shannon révèle que seules les trouées d'abattage ($H' = 3,04$) et les pistes de débardage ($H' = 2,95$) sont plus diversifiées que le site témoin ($H' = 2,87$). Sur ce dernier site, les espèces non commerciales et les espèces

commerciales de Classe 1 ont affiché des plus grandes proportions (22 % chacune), alors que les espèces des autres classes présentent des proportions importantes sur les sites exploités. Hormis les routes, la diversité des sites exploités est inversement proportionnelle à l'intensité des opérations. Des opérations post-exploitation de suivi sylvicole s'avèrent

donc nécessaires en vue de rentabiliser les effets positifs et minimiser les effets négatifs de l'exploitation industrielle du bois d'œuvre. Les résultats de cette étude peuvent servir de piste pour guider les exploitants dans la planification harmonieuse de leurs opérations en vue d'en garantir la durabilité.

Mots clés : Exploitation forestière, Diversité spécifique, composition floristique

1. Introduction

Specific diversity and floristic composition analysis of tropical forests are becoming more and more mandatory regarding the increasingly pressure on forest ecosystems (WCMC, 1992; Ouédraogo et al., 2011; Mayaux et al., 2013; FAO, 2015). Many studies have showed that these two floristic parameters are directly influenced by many factors among which the disturbances are the most preminent. (Klinge et al., 1995; Hugaasen et al., 2003; Wittmann and Junk, 2003). These disturbances cause floristic variation according to its intensity, its frequency (Hill and Curran, 2003; Laidlaw et al., 2007; Waldron et al., 2014) and the spreading of logged area (Belesi, 2009) and could also alter forest diversities and compositions. The industrial logging is numerated among the forest disturbances and its effects on the flora require a specific attention (Jonkers, 2000; Obame, 2014; FAO, 2015). This attention seems to be imminent in the Democratic Republic of Congo, (DRC) because the area covered by this form of practices is widely represented in forest concessions which represent 7.8 % of the entire forest of the country which is, approximately 12.5 million ha and has an annual increase of more than 100 000 ha.

Based on its characteristics, the industrial logging has a considerable impact on forest ecosystem services. Many collateral disturbances are inferred to the industrial logging among which figure out the wood filling, which leads to non-target wood fall (White et al., 1994; Waldron et al., 2013). It creates openings in the forest, leading in one hand to regeneration problems of some species due to the rapid drying up of the soil and the loss of its nutrients (Fordjour et al., 2009) and in the other hand, to the growth of invasive species and other herbaceous plants that prevent the tree and shrub species from recovering the area (Epp, 1987; Hawthorne et Jongkind, 2006 ; Madoffe et al., 2006). This activity also causes the crushing of diaspores buried superficially in the ground because of the trauma caused by the fallen trees (Condit et al., 2012; Obame, 2014).

Up to now, there are not any studies based on the assessment of logging impacts on floristic diversity

and composition in DRC. Yet, understanding industrial logging effects on floristic biodiversity and finding a compromise between positive and negative effects resulted are one of the fundamental elements for the sustainable management of forests (Doucet, 2003; Gillet, 2006; Belesi, 2009; Obame, 2014). In this propose, this studies is attempting to give a basic answer to the problematic above mentioned. The main objective of this study is to determine and analyze the impact of the industrial logging on the specific diversity and floristic composition of a forest. From the result of this study, a lot of information will be derived in order to allow forest managers to improve the suitability of logging forests by knowing the maximum intensity of logging to apply in different points of impact.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Study area

The investigation has been done in the forest concession of Cotrefor-Alibuku (N°018/011) of 277 033 ha. The concession is located at N 0°40' - 1°20'; E 25°10' and 26°00' in the Oriental province, the district of Tshopo. The concession is governed by a hot and humid climate. The mean annual rainfall is about 1700 mm/year. The temperature reaches an average of 23.9° C (min: 19° C and max: 30° C). The mean relative humidity is about 82 % (min: 81 % and max: 83 %). The forest concession is covered by 56 % of secondary forest, 26 % of primary terra-firma forest, 3 % of swamp forest and 15 % of anthropogenic area.

2.2. Choice of sampling areas and data collection

A part from the undisturbed site, four categories of impact points were considered: the logging roads, the skid trails, the log landing and the logging gaps. In total, 20 sites were selected in the Annual Standing Cup operated between January 2013 and February 2014. For the skid trails, a random forest inventory was carried out within rectangular plots of a surface unit area of 30 m². The inventory plots were installed in the middle of each individual skid trail and distributed in 5 different areas. Each area had its specific "operation intensity", that is to say that less than 50, 50-100, 100-200, 200-300 and more than

300 m³ of wood unloaded through the set of skid trail. It is important to denote that a repetition was applied for each plot in order to have in total 5 plots.

For the logging gaps, the prior work consisted of identifying those undisturbed, blowdown and human activities, after the forest logging. Four among them were chosen according to their intensity of operation; that is to say that the cut down tree volume in m³: less than 5, 5-15, 15-25 and more than 25 m³. We established triangular plots of 30 m² (12 m x 5 m). The triangular form was preferred in accordance with the general form of a logging gap and in the objective of avoiding area not touched by tree-fall. Concerning the logging roads, random plots of 30 m² were settled in the two main roads of the Annual Standing Cup of 2013. Five plots in the first main road of 19.7 km in length and 2 plots on the second main road of 6.59 km in length. In all cases, plots were settled in stretches which were never been disturbed after the logging. Similar to the skid trails and all other surveyed impact points, stretches on which plots have been randomly settled are differentiated by their “intensity of operation”, that is to say that the quantity in m³ of transported woods: less than 100, 100-200, 200-300, 300-400, 400-500, 500-600 and more than 600 m³. For each “intensity of operation”, a repetition was applied.

For the log landings, rectangular plots of 30 m² were established which are differentiated, as for other points of impact, by their “intensity of operation” that is to say that the quantity in m³ of woods which were interposed: less than 300, 300-400, 400-500 and more than 500 m³. In total, 4 plots were settled in light of one repetition per “intensity of operation”. All these areas were chosen in the same type of forest ecosystem (dense forest with hydromorph trend) where logging operations have been concentrated.

In each plot, all stems of diameter greater than 1 cm were inventoried through a systematic counting. The altitude of the site and intensity of logging operations were also noted for each plot. The intensity of

Figure 1 : Sample plots size

operations was expressed in m³ of tree transported, hauled, stored and fall respectively on the operating roads, the skid trails, the wood yards (log landing) and the logging gaps sampled.

2.3. Data analysis

The species diversity is here expressed by of specific and generic richness and also diversity and distribution indexes. The species richness is the total number of species in a population (Ramade, 1994). It has been calculated by an independent inventory surface index and it is based on the abundance, S_{Chao2} . Where S_{obs} is the observed species richness, $Q1$ is exactly the number of species in one sample (unique) and $Q2$ is the number of species in exactly two samples (double).

$$S_{Chao2} = S_{obs} + (Q_1^2/2Q_2) \tag{Eq. 1}$$

The generic richness was obtained through the index or specific ratio calculated by Szymkiewicz formula (Schmitz, 1971). Where S_p is the total number of species inventoried and G the total number of genus.

$$Q_s = \frac{S_p}{G} \tag{Eq. 2}$$

Diversity indexes have been used in order to measure the quality, the functionality, the viability and the evolution of flora. The indexes used in this study are: the Morisita-Horn index, the Shannon-Weaver index, the Simpson index and the equitability index of Pielou. The Morisita-Horn index (MHij) has been used to test whether the different areas have different floristic compositions (Hurlbert 1971).

Figure 2 : Location of sampling areas

Table 1 : The taxonomic richness of the study site

Sites	Families	Genuses	Species	Qs	S _{Chao} ²	% (S _{obs} /S _{Chao} ²)
Log landing	17	27	30	1.111	37.68	79.6
Skid trail	26	49	56	1.143	67.28	83.2
Road	25	45	50	1.111	52.72	88.2
Control site	16	23	23	1.000	-	-
Logging gap	18	32	34	1.063	54.05	62.9

$$MH_{ij} = \frac{\sum_i P_{is} \times P_{js}}{(\sum_i P_{is}^2 + \sum_j P_{js}^2)}$$

Eq. 3

This coefficient has been calculated automatically with BiodivR 1.0 software. A «cluster analysis» has been produced with the MVSP software in order to establish a differential dendrogram. The index of Shannon-Weaver (H') has been used to estimate the degree of ecological integrity of the sites.

$$H' = - \sum_{P_i} P_i \log_2 P_i$$

Eq. 4

Where P_i = N_i / N. with, N = total number of individuals of all species; N_i = number of individuals of a species i. The Simpson index (D) has been used to make a conclusion on the accuracy of results obtained with the Shannon index (Frontier and Pichod, 1995).

$$D = \sum (P_i)^2$$

Eq. 5

The equitability index has been used to assess the species regularity in each site.

$$E(R) = \frac{H'}{H'_{max}}$$

Eq. 6

In order to highlight the different potential strategies between floristic groups (Khi-square test of independence), the distribution of flora life of habitats of each site has been assessed. The species feature considered are (Letouzey, 1983) the morphological form (tree, shrub, grass and liana), the seed dispersal (autochore, zoochore and anémochore) and the market value (non-commercial species, species class 1, class 2, class 3 and Class 4) (MECNT, 2009). A Canonical Correspondence Analysis has been performed to detect the extent of floristic variation explained by the altitude and the logging intensity. At least, to test the effect of the descriptive variables and their interactions; a permutation test has been applied by using 1,000 permutations.

3. Results

3.1. The taxonomic richness of the study site

A total of 72 species belonging to 30 families and

Figure 3: The most represented families

Table 2 : The similarity matrix of Morisita-Horn

Sites	Log landing	Skid trail	Roads	Control site	Logging gap
Log landing	1.000000	0.927735	0.962111	0.065669	0.260756
Skid trail	0.927735	1.000000	0.903907	0.134950	0.339612
Roads	0.962111	0.903907	1.000000	0.114254	0.271338
Control site	0.065669	0.134950	0.114254	1.000000	0.218993
Logging gap	0.260756	0.339612	0.271338	0.218993	1.000000

62 genres have been identified. The different sites affected by logging have shown a greater richness compared to the undisturbed site (control site). The skid trails reveals the greatest richness (table 1). The control site shows the lowest value of Specific Quotient than all operated sites. This reveals the negative contribution of logging on the maturation and stability of flora in the area because the more the index is great, the more unstable the flora is considered (Lebrun, 1960). The ratio of species richness between the exploited sites and the control site is about 1.3 for the yard; 2.4 for the skid trail; 2.2 for the logging road and 1.5 for the felling of trees. This ratio leads to a conclusion according to which, the skid trail and the logging road have almost twice as many species as the control site. The estimated species richness has the largest proportion compared to the richness observed on roads (88.2%).

In general, the 5 most represented families are the same in all disturbed sites (figure 2). In chronological order, we can enumerate the families of *Euphorbiaceae*, *Rubiaceae*, *Fabaceae*, *Moraceae* and *Apocynaceae*. The families of *Euphorbiaceae* and *Rubiaceae* are the most represented in all sites affected by logging. They respectively take the first two places except in the logging gaps where family of *Fabaceae* took the second place. These families are better represented in the sites affected by logging because of the presence of sun-loving species such as *Macaranga div. sp* and *Musanga cecropioides*. On the control site, the families of *Fabaceae* and *Apocynaceae* are the most predominant. The family of *Fabaceae* has the highest number of species in the control site because it can tolerate both the sun and the shadow. The effective representativeness of families of *Malvaceae* and *Meliaceae* in the control site is detected by the strong presence of some species such as *Scaphopeta lumthonneri* and *Guarea cedrata*. These two species are the most important species of the site and record the largest index of indicative value (IVI) or respectively 17% and 11%.

3.2. Similarity and floristic composition

The similarity level of different sites studied is expressed here by the similarity matrix of Morisita-Horn (table 2). This index provides information that the control site has no similarity in terms of species composition with different impact points in so far as the similarity index found are all less than 0.5.

This observation is also made for logging gaps that develop a flora quite different from that found on all other sites. However, there is a strong floristic similarity between log landing, skid trails and roads. This observation is completed and clarified by the dendrogram on figure 3.

Below a Euclidean distance of 200, there is a great floristic similarity between the log landings and the skid trails. Considering the same Euclidean distance, we see that the entire flora found in these sites is similar to that found on the roads. With a Euclidean distance greater than 1000, the flora of logging gaps, despite having one of the lowest species richness observed, is the richest and has similarities with the entire flora of all other sites.

3.3. Floristic diversity and species characteristic

At the floristic diversity, logging gaps and skid trails are the most floristically stable site and lead to a diversified flora establishment (table 3). Roads and log landings record a certain species with significantly greater abundance and some others with very low abundance. These observations are supported by the coefficient of Simpson.

Figure 4 : Dendrogram of sites according to the floristic similarity

Table 3 : Index of diversity in different sites

Sites	Index of Shannon-Weaver	Index of Pielou	Simpson coefficient
Control site	2,874	0,917	0.829
Roads	2,660	0,680	0.868
Skid trails	2,952	0,733	0.849
Log landings	2,409	0,708	0.926
Logging gaps	3,044	0,863	0.928

Table 4 : Abundance (in %) of life of habitats for 5 sites

Life of habitats	Component	Log landing	Roads	Logging gaps	Skid trails	Control site	Independent test result χ^2
Type of plant	Tree	77,21	74,05	47,44	70,13	60,78	$\chi^2=844$; ddl=12 ; p<0,001 (H ₀ is rejected)
	Shrub	14,22	18,16	43,59	22,10	17,65	
	Grass	3,68	5,17	7,05	4,85	17,65	
	Liana	4,90	2,61	1,92	2,93	3,92	
Dispersal mode	Autochore	5,66	11,16	21,15	16,19	54,92	$\chi^2=304$; ddl=8 ; p<0,001 (H ₀ is rejected)
	Zoochore	80,75	11,73	69,88	77,02	41,18	
	Anemochore	13,59	77,11	8,97	6,79	3,90	
Commercial value	N.C.S.	6,87	8,48	20,51	9,02	21,57	$\chi^2=1245$; ddl=16 ; p<0,001 (H ₀ is rejected)
	Class 1	15,47	16,93	8,97	9,02	21,57	
	Class 2	38,01	37,36	7,05	38,24	17,65	
	Class 3	4,89	5,33	3,21	3,95	3,92	
	Class 4	34,77	31,90	60,26	39,76	35,29	

N.C.S.: Non Commercial Species

More than 50 species found on roads, 37 have dominance (abundance) of less than 5% and only 13 species have dominance above 5%. In this site, two species clearly dominate because they have dominance above 10%. These species are *Musanga cecropioides* (DF = 33%) and *Aidiam icrantha* (DF = 12%). These species are typically of roads.

Furthermore, 10 species have dominance less than 1%. This is the case of *Sarcocephalus pobeguinii*, *Croto nhaumanianus*, *Funtumia elastica*, *Trilepisium madagascariense*, *Blighia welwitschii*, *Chrysophyllum lacourtianum*, *Macaranga laurentii*, *Staudtia kamerunensis*, *Ctenitisprotensa var. speciosa*, *Massularia acuminata*.

5 species may be considered as indicative in log landing. Among which are enumerated *Musanga cecropioides* (IVI = 37%), *Aidiami crantha* (IVI = 10%), *Dialium excelsum* (IVI = 9.1%), *Pterocarpus soyauxii* (IVI = 7.8%) and *Macaranga spinosa* (IVI = 6.6%). In addition to these dominant species, we will find 16 species having an index of indicator value (IVI) of less than 1%. Overall, the most important species found on different sites affected by logging belong to the class of *Musango-Terminalietea* which is the class of secondary forest species and dominated by sun-loving species.

3.4. Specific richness and floristic composition according to the life of habitats

The effects of disturbance on flora are expressed differently according to the group of species. The representation in terms of abundance of three lives of habitats in different study sites are shown in the table 4. All life of habitats studied reveal dependencies with the studied sites in terms of the number of individuals identified (chi-square test : p<0,001). The proportion of trees is lower in the control site than in the exploited ones (except logging gaps) while liana species (4%) and herbaceous (18%) have a high proportion in the control site.

The strongest relationship between the life of habitats and the site is linked to the market value : the noncommercial species and commercial species of Class 1 are more abundant in the control site (22%). These of Class 4 are predominant on the skid trails and the logging gaps (40% and 60% respectively). The roads and the log landings are predominated by commercial species of Class 2.

3.5. Relation between the specific diversity, altitude and logging intensity

The results of the permutation test conducted with 1,000 permutations show that the effects of logging

Table 5 : Permutation test result

	Permutation	Pseudo F	p-value	alpha	Test result
Log landings	1,000	1.39	0.60	0.05	H ₀ is accepted
Skid trails	1,000	1.97	0.06	0.05	H ₀ is accepted
Roads	1,000	0.95	0.59	0.05	H ₀ is accepted
Logging gaps	1,000	1.63	0.08	0.05	H ₀ is accepted

Table 6 : Partition (in %) of floristic variance

Studied sites	Inertia	Value	%	F1	F2
Log landings	Constrain inertia	0.66	73.59	79.669	20.331
	Non constrain inertia	0.24	26.40	58.633	14.963
Skid trails	Constrain inertia	0.97	66.40	55.623	44.377
	Non constrain inertia	0.49	33.59	36.937	29.469
Roads	Constrain inertia	0.37	32.25	60.055	39.945
	Non constrain inertia	0.78	67.75	19.367	12.882
Logging gaps	Constrain inertia	0.97	76.50	59.859	40.141
	Non constrain inertia	0.29	23.49	45.793	30.708

on flora depend on the altitude and the intensity of operations (table 5). This variation is not linear and dependent on the site. Thus, in order to determine the part of the flora variance explained by the selected two variables, the different values of inertia of the canonical axes obtained for each site were calculated (table 6).

It is important to denote that 65% of the total variance observed in the floristic diversity of the logged sites is explained by the altitude and the intensity of logging operations. The effect of these two variables is more pronounced in the logging gaps (77%) and the log landings (74%). For all studied sites, most of the observed variance is explained by the first axis. In order to understand simultaneously the correlation between different variables studied at each site, a correlation of the variables was established (figure 4). We can see that most of the floristic diversity of log landings (1) is negatively correlated with the altitude and the volume of woods stored (Operations intensity). This means that the intensive logging operation at the log landings leads to the reduction in species diversity.

However, 4 species (*Pterocarpus soyauxii*, *Milicia excelsa*, *Musanga cecropioides* and *Nauclea diderichii*) are positively correlated with the two explicative variables. All these four sun-loving species have been identified with recurrence in the log landings of large volume of wood during logging and are located at an altitude relatively high. It is the

Figure 4 : Correlogram of log landings (1), logging gaps (2), skid trails (3) and roads (4)

same for the logging gaps (2) where the increase of the altitude and intensity of operations (or volume of harvested timber) induced negatively floristic diversity. In the logging roads (4) and skid trails (3), the situation is almost similar.

4. Discussion

This study demonstrated that logging could have a positive impact on flora. This positive impact is

Table 7: Density obtained in comparison with other authors (stem/100m²)

Sites	Gillet, (2013)	Kouadio et al. (2007)	The present study
Control site	167 ± 75	82,26 ± 137,30	110,87 ± 95,29
Log landings	-	-	11,61 ± 23,71
Logging gaps	233 ± 145	85,54 ± 142,92	115,91 ± 141,39
Roads	-	-	14,50 ± 37,20
Skid trails	82 ± 74	-	10,56 ± 26,88

especially important in terms of taxonomic richness. These results corroborate those found by other researchers (Berges et al., 2013; Kouadio et al., 2007; Frederiksen and Mostacedo, 2000; Boyemba, 2011; Ouédraogo et al., 2011). The lower value of the specific quotient has been obtained in the control site. This means that logging contributes to the flora instability, although the fact that it increases species richness (Lubini, 1982; Waldron et al., 2014). This information is supported by the Indicator Value Indexes (IVI) which report that the species indicator of the sites affected by logging belong to the class of *Musango-Terminalietea* whereas *Strombosio-Parinarietea* characterizes the control site.

This floristic instability induced by logging is benefic, not only in terms of specific richness, but also and especially in terms of species richness and value of forest regeneration (Belesi, 2013). Indeed, tree species, shrubs and commercial species are more abundant in the sites affected by logging than in the control site. Skid trails are the most favorable in terms of the richness of value species. This result was also found by Swaine and Agyeman (2008). As far as the types of diaspore are concerned, more than 80% of important species of the sites affected by logging are sarchochores. According to Dansereau and Lems (1957), Everard (1968), Lubini (1997), Masens (1997), Ngok (2005) and Mullenders (1954), this type of diaspore characterizes species whose dissemination is caused by animals or humans. The preponderance of sarchochores species in logged sites could be explained by the effect of human (operating teams) on seed dispersal. At the site not affected by logging, it has been noted that the two important species of the site are all autochores. This corroborates the results found by many other authors including Doucet (2003) and Obame (2014) who confirmed the dominance of autochorie in the evergreen rainfall forest at the Congo basin.

From the perspective of the global diversity, it is important to denote that the diversity of roads, log

landings and skid trails is less than that found in the control site. The logging gaps are the only point of impact having a positive impact on overall plant diversity of the forest. The Species richness and the floristic composition are higher than in the unlogged forest. The high density of logging gaps has also been reported by other authors (table 7).

In this study, the hypothesis of the change in floral composition according to the altitude and the intensity of the logging site were issued. As expected, the results showed that these two variables contribute to the variation in species composition of the logged sites (Berges et al., 2013). Great intensity from operating activities negatively influences the post-operating floristic composition because more than 50% of species identified on the affected sites are negatively correlated with this variable: 66.6% for log landings, 54% for roads, 61% for skid trails and 70.6% for logging gaps.

5. Conclusion

One year after the industrial logging, the study showed that the forest is resilient to logging operation. All the points of impact showed a greater species richness than the control site. The results have also confirmed that the increasing volume of wood hauled on the skid trails and wood volume stored in the log landings reduces post-operation floristic diversity.

Despite their high species richness, the overall low floristic diversity of sites affected by logging and the high abundance of herbaceous species and liana on these sites indicate the need to monitor post-exploitation operations followed by regeneration in order to control the competition and to increase the regeneration of commercial species, which effectively contributes to sustainable forest management.

Acknowledgments

We gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Transport and Logging Company (Cotrefor), especially Roberto Delbene who made this support possible and Nicolas Bayol who made possible the

link with Cotrefor. We thank also the Germano-Congolese nonprofit NGO Förderverein Uni Kinshasa e.V for several kinds of support.

References

- Belesi, H. K. (2009).** Etude floristique, phytogéographique et phytosociologique de la végétation du Bas-Kasai en RDC. *Thèse inédit, UNIKIN, Fac. Sciences.* 565pp.
- Berges, L., Chevalier R., Avon C. (2013).** Influence of forest road, road surfacing material and stand age on floristic diversity and composition in a nutrient-poor environment. *Applied Vegetation Science.* 16 : 470-479.
- Boyemba, F. B. (2011).** Ecologie de *Pericopsis elata* (Harms) Van Meeuwen, arbre de forêt tropicale africaine à répartition agrégée. *Unpublished PhD Thesis.* ULB. 206pp.
- Condit Richard, Chisholm Ryan A., Hubbell Stephen., P. (2012).** Thirty Years of Forest Census at Barro Colorado and the Importance of Immigration in Maintaining Diversity. *PLoS ONE 7(11):* 1-6.
- Doucet, J.L. (2003).** L'alliance délicate de la gestion forestière et de la biodiversité dans les forêts du centre du Gabon. *Unpublished PhD Thesis, Gembloux AgroBioTech.* 390pp.
- Epp, GA. (1987).** The seed bank of *Eupatorium odoratum* along a successional gradient in a tropical rain forest in Ghana. *J. Trop. Ecol.* 3: 139-149.
- Evrard, C. (1968).** Recherches écologiques sur le peuplement forestier des sols hydromorphes de la cuvette centrale congolaise. *O.N.R.D./ INEAC, Sér. Sc. 110. Bruxelles* 295 p.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (2015).** Global Forest Resources Assessment 2015 *Desk reference, Rome,* 253p
- Fordjour, S., Obeng, A. K., Anning, M. G., Addo. (2009).** Floristic composition, structure and natural regeneration in a moist semi-deciduous forest following anthropogenic disturbances and plant invasion. *International Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation* Vol. 1 (2): 021-037.
- Fredericksen, T. S., et Mostacedo, D. (2000).** Regeneration of timber species following selection logging in a Bolivian tropical dry forest. *Forest Ecology and Management,* vol. 131 (1-3): 47-55. (USA).
- Frontier, S. et Pichod-Viale, D. (1995).** Ecosystèmes : Structures, fonctionnement évolution. *Collection d'Ecologie 21. Masson, 2^{ème} édition, Paris,* 477p.
- Gillet, J. F. (2006).** Formations végétales, régénération et impact de l'exploitation forestière en forêt mixte de terre ferme au nord de la République du Congo. *Mémoire de DEA, Gembloux AgroBioTech.* 194pp.
- Gillet, J. F. (2013).** Les forêts à Marantaceae au sein de la mosaïque forestière du Nord de la République du Congo : Origines et Modalités de gestion. *Unpublished PhD Thesis, Gembloux AgroBioTech.* 193pp.
- Haugaasen T., Barlow J., Peres CA. (2003).** Surface wildfires in central Amazonia: Short-term impact on forest structure and carbon loss. *For. Ecol. Manage.* 179: 321-331.
- Hawthorne W. D. and Jongking C. (2006).** Woody plants of the forest trees, shrubs and lianas from Senegal to Ghana, *Ed. Royal Botanic Garden, Kew; Wageningen University* (1023p).
- Hill JL, Curran P. J. (2003).** Area, shape and isolation of tropical forest fragments: effects on tree species diversity and implications for conservation forest area. *J. Biogeogr.* 30: 1391-1403.
- Hurlbert, S. H. (1971).** The nonconcept of species diversity: a critique and alternative parameters. *Ecology* 52:577-586.
- Jonkers, W. (ed.) (2000).** Logging, damage and efficiency: a study on the feasibility of Reduced Impact Logging in Cameroon. Final report, Tropenbos-Cameroon Programme, Kribi (Cameroon). *Wageningen University, Wageningen.*
- Klinge, H., Adis J., Worbes M. (1995).** The vegetation of a seasonal várzea in the lower Solimõesriver, *Brazilian Amazon. Acta Amazonica* 25: 201-220.
- Kouadio, K., Kouassi, K. E., Kouamé, N. F. et Traoré, D. (2007).** Impact de l'éclaircie sur la régénération naturelle des essences principales, dans la forêt classée de Bossematié (Côte d'Ivoire). *Sciences et Nature* 4 (1) : 27-35.
- Laidlaw, M., Kitching, R., Goodall K., Small A., Stork N. (2007).** Temporal and spatial variation in an Australian tropical rainforest. *Austral Ecol.* 32: 10-20.
- Lebrun, J. (1960).** Etude de la flore et de la végétation des champs de la lave au nord du lac Kivu. 392 p.

- Expl. Parc Nat. Albert, Mission J.Lebrun, Fasc. 2, Bruxelles, Inst. des parcs nationaux du Congo belge.*
- Lebrun, J., et Gilbert G. (1954).** Une classification écologique des forêts du Congo, 89 p. *Publ. INEAC, Sér. Sc. 63 Bruxelles.*
- Letouzey, R. (1983).** Manuel de botanique forestière. *Afrique Tropicale, 3 Tomes, CTFT, Nogent-sur-Marne.*
- Lubini, A. (1982).** Végétation messicole et post-culturale des Sous-Régions de Kisangani et de la Tshopo (Haut-Zaïre). 489p. *Thèse de doctorat, Université de Kisangani Fac. Sci.*
- Lubini A. (1997).** La végétation de la Réserve de Biosphère de Luki au Mayombe (Zaïre). 155p. *Jard. Bot. Nat. Belg. Opera Meise 10.*
- Madoffe S., Hertel G. D., Rodgers P., O'Connell B., Killenga R. (2006).** Monitoring the health of selected eastern arc forests in Tanzania. *Afr. J. Ecol. 44: 171-177.*
- Masens, D. M. Y. (1997).** Etude phytosociologique de la région de Kikwit (Bandundu, RDC), 398 p. *Thèse de doctorat. Fac. Sc. ULB-Belgique.12101101.*
- Mayaux, P., Pekel, J.F., Desclée, B., Donnay, F., Lupi, A., Achard, F., Clerici, M., Bodart, C., Brink, A. et Nasi, R. (2013).** State and evolution of the African rainforests between 1990 and 2010. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences 368 (1625).*
- Ministère de l'Environnement, Conservation de la Nature et Tourisme (MCNT) de la RDC/Direction d'inventaire et d'Aménagement Forestier (DIAF) (2009).** Guide opérationnel : *Liste des essences forestières de la République Démocratique du Congo.* 56p
- Mullenders, W. (1954).** La végétation de Kaniama (entre Lubishi-Lubilash, Congo belge). 499 P. *Publ. INEAC Sér.Sc. 61.*
- Ngok, B. L. (2005).** Diversité végétale des Inselberg et des dalles rocheuses du nord Gabon. 420 p. *Thèse de Doctorat, ULB, Belgique.*
- Obame, J. P. E. (2014).** Structure spatiale et dispersion des communautés d'arbres en forêt tropicale humide du Gabon : rôle des facteurs édaphiques et du gradient de chablis, *Thèse de doctorat, Université Laval, Faculté de Foresterie, Géographie et Géomatique, 122p*
- Ouédraogo, D.-Y., Beina D., Picard, N., Mortier, F., Baya, F., Gourlet-Fleury, S. (2011).** Thinning after selective logging facilitates floristic composition recovery in a tropical rain forest of Central Africa. *Forest Ecology Management 262, 2176-2186*
- Ramade, F. (1994).** Eléments d'écologie. Ecologie fondamentale 2. *Ediscience internationale, Paris. 579p.*
- Schmitz, A. (1971).** La végétation de la plaine de Lubumbashi (Haut-Katanga). 388 p. *illustrations. INEAC, Sér. Sc. 113. Bruxelles.*
- Swaine, M. D. et Agyeman V.K. (2008).** Enhanced tree recruitment following logging in two Forest Reserves in Ghana. *Biotropica 40 (3): 370-374.*
- Waldron, K., Ruel, J.-C. and Gauthier, S. (2013).** The effects of site characteristics on the landscape-level windthrow regime in the North Shore region of Quebec, Canada *Forestry ; 86, 159–171, doi:10.1093/forestry/cps061.*
- Waldron, K., Ruel, J.-C., Gauthier, S., De Grandpre, L. and Peterson, C. J. (2014).** Effects of post-windthrow salvage logging on microsites, plant composition and regeneration. *Applied Vegetation Science 17 (2014) 323-337.*
- WCMC (1992).** World Conservation Monitoring Centre. *Global Biodiversity: Status of Earth's Living Resources. Chapman and Hall, London, UK.*
- White, G. M., Boshier D. H., Powell W. (1999).** Genetic variation within a fragmented population of *Swietenia humilis Zucc. Molecular Ecology, 8, PP. 1899-1909.*
- Wittmann, F., Junk W. J. (2003).** Sapling communities in Amazonian whitewater forests. *J. Biogeogr. 30: 1533-1544.*